
CASE COMMENT ON INOX RENEWABLE LTD V. JAYESH ELECTRICAL LTD.

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ABSTRACT

Arbitration is a private dispute resolution process where parties decide to settle their dispute instead of going to court. The main features of arbitration process are confidentiality, neutrality and it is consensual. The arbitral award is final and binding on both parties.² Party autonomy is also a key feature of arbitration process. Party autonomy means parties are free to decide which substantive law would apply, number of arbitrators, seat, and venue of arbitration. The seat of arbitration is vitally important as it determines the applicable law to the arbitration proceedings. Seat of arbitration is different from venue of arbitration as the former determines which procedural laws would apply to the arbitration proceedings and the latter is merely the geographical location where the proceedings would take place. It is important that parties must mutually determine the seat of arbitration to avoid unnecessary dispute. This content aims at providing the information about case decided upon the validity of the subsequent change of seat of arbitration by mutual agreement. In this judgment, the court has laid importance upon the shifting of seat of arbitration by mutual agreement of the parties.

Keywords: Seat of arbitration, mutual agreement, venue of arbitration, shifting of seat, jurisdiction

I. BACKGROUND

The confusion between the terms ‘seat’ and ‘venue’ of arbitration has always been a point of dispute. Venue means the geographical location where arbitration proceeding take place and seat means the place where arbitration is anchored. In this case the Division Bench of the Supreme Court consisting of Justice Rohinton F. Nariman and Justice Hrishikesh Roy decided on the point of seat and venue of arbitration where the question before Hon’ble

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² The Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996, § 35, No. 26, Acts of Parliament, 1996 (India)

Supreme Court was whether the seat of arbitration selected by the parties could be changed later by mutual agreement between the parties, which was not in writing. The Supreme Court has settled the question of law regarding the shifting of seat of arbitration and the change in the jurisdiction of the court due to such shifting of seat of arbitration.³

II. FACTS OF THE CASE

In the present case, on 28th January 2012 a purchase order was entered into between Gujarat Fluorochemicals Ltd. (GFL) and the respondent Jayesh Electricals Ltd. (JEL) for the manufacture and supply of power transformers at wind farm. The purchase order in its arbitration clause mentions that all disputes and differences shall be settled by arbitration which shall be conducted by three arbitrators (one nominated by each party and third will be an umpire). Also, the venue of arbitration shall be Jaipur. If either of the party is not satisfied with the arbitrators' award, they can seek lawful remedies under the law of India. The jurisdiction for such actions will be the courts situated in the State of Rajasthan.⁴

A Business Transfer Agreement (BTA) dated 30th March 2012 was executed between Gujarat Fluorochemicals Ltd. (GFL) and Inox Renewables Ltd appellant herein, through which the entire business of GFL was transferred to Inox Renewable Ltd. The respondent (JEL) was not a party to the Business Transfer Agreement. The BTA fixed Vadodara as the seat of arbitration and the courts in Vadodara were given the exclusive jurisdiction over the disputes arising out of the same.

Later, on 5th September 2014 an application under Section 11 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996 was filed with the High Court of Gujarat at Ahmedabad by the respondent (JEL) for the appointment of an arbitrator under the purchase order. A sole arbitrator was appointed by the court based on joint submission by both parties. An award dated 28th July 2018 was passed in the favour of the respondent awarding a sum of Rs 38,97,150/- plus as interest on the arbitral award, from 10th March 2017 till the date of passing of arbitral award, a sum of Rs. 31,32,650 was also awarded to JEL, along with quantified costs amounting to Rs. 2,81,000. Further, 15% future interest was awarded from the date of award till the date of payment.⁵

³ Bar and Bench, The Viewpoint: Can parties change the seat of arbitration through mutual agreement? (Nov. 13, 2023, 04:52 PM), <https://www.barandbench.com/law-firms/view-point/can-parties-change-seat-of-arbitration-through-mutual-agreement>

⁴ Inox Renewables Ltd. v. Jayesh Electricals Ltd, (2023) 3 SCC 733

⁵ Indian Kanoon, <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/6809742/> (last visited 14th Nov. 2023)

Aggrieved by the award, appellate filed Section 34 petition in Commercial Court of Ahmedabad. The respondent opposed the said petition and relying on the Business Transfer Agreement argued that Vadodara courts alone have jurisdiction. The Commercial Court through an order dated 25th April 2019 dismissed the application and held that the courts at Vadodara had exclusive jurisdiction.

Aggrieved by the judgment of the Commercial Court of Ahmedabad the appellant filed a special civil application before the Gujarat High Court. The High Court relying upon the arbitration clause of the purchase order held that since exclusive jurisdiction is vested in the courts at Rajasthan the appropriate court would be the court at Jaipur and rejected the application. But the court didn't find any error in the judgment and order of Commercial court of Ahmedabad.

The Appellate (Inox Renewable Ltd.) filed an appeal before the Apex Court challenging the judgment passed by the Gujarat High Court.

III. ISSUE

The before the Apex Court was whether the seat designated by the agreement could be changed by a subsequent mutual agreement between the parties.

IV. ARGUMENTS BY THE PARTIES

The appellant contended that since the Business Transfer Agreement was not executed between the appellant and respondent it is irrelevant in the present case. Also, the Gujarat High Court has failed to take into account the fact that arbitrator has recorded in the arbitral award that the venue/place of arbitration was shifted by mutual consent of the parties to Ahmedabad.⁶ (Parties mutually agreed that irrespective of the specific clause the venue of the arbitration would be at Ahmedabad and not at Jaipur) As a result of which exclusive jurisdiction would lie with the courts of Ahmedabad. Appellate relied upon the case of BGS SGS Soma JV v. NHPC Ltd. (2019) in which the court held that when a particular place is designated as the venue of arbitration the same should be considered to be the seat of arbitration.⁷

⁶Nilava Bandyopadhyay, Adhip Kumar Ray, The Viewpoint: Can parties change the seat of arbitration through mutual agreement?, Bar and Bench, (Nov. 14, 2023, 04:52 PM), <https://www.barandbench.com/law-firms/view-point/can-parties-change-seat-of-arbitration-through-mutual-agreement>

⁷Hiroo Advani, Sheikh Yusuf Ali and Manav Nagpal, Seat v. Venue in Contemporary Arbitral Jurisprudence, SCC Online, (Nov. 15, 2023, 05:15 PM), <https://www.scconline.com/blog/post/2021/05/06/seat-v-venue-in-contemporary-arbitral-jurisprudence/>

Relying upon the judgment in *Videocon Industries Ltd. v. Union of India* (2011) and *Indus Mobile Distribution Private Ltd. v. Datawind Innovations Private Ltd.* (2017) the respondent contended that even if the venue was shifted from Jaipur to Ahmedabad by mutual agreement, it cannot be done without a written agreement between the parties. It was further argued that the shifting of venue of arbitration from Jaipur to Ahmedabad was merely with reference to Section 20(3) of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996 because Ahmedabad was a convenient place. Therefore, even if the venue was shifted to Ahmedabad the seat of arbitration will be Jaipur only.

V. JUDGMENT

Allowing the appeal filed by Inox Renewables the hon'ble court after hearing the arguments of both the sides held the following:

1. From the arbitral award passed by the arbitrator it is evident that both the parties had mutually agreed to shift the place/venue of arbitration from Ahmedabad to Jaipur So, respondent's argument that written agreement was necessary for shifting the venue or place of arbitration from Jaipur to Ahmedabad cannot be accepted. Accordingly, here shifting was in reference to both seat and venue and not only venue.
2. The respondent relied upon the case of *Videocon Industries Ltd. v. Union of India* on the point that seat can be shifted only by a written agreement signed by the parties. It is to be noted that in *Videocon* case the parties in the arbitration agreement had an amendment which specified that any change in the seat of arbitration can be made only by way of written agreement which was to be signed by all of them. However, in the present case neither the Purchase Order nor the Business Transfer Agreement had any clause which mentions that the shifting of seat of arbitration can done only by written agreement. Also, neither party challenged the arbitrator's award. Hence the judgment of *Videocon* will have no application in this case.
3. The respondent also relied upon the case of *Indus Mobile Distribution Private Ltd. v. Datawind Innovations Private Ltd.* The contention of the counsel of respondent that the jurisdiction of courts in Rajasthan is independent of the venue being at Jaipur does not stands correct. The dispute resolution clause of the purchase order must be read as a whole. The arbitration clause and jurisdiction clause must be read

together as the courts in Rajasthan have been vested with jurisdiction only because the seat was to be at Jaipur.

Since the seat of arbitration was shifted to Ahmedabad by mutual agreement of both parties and Jaipur no longer continue to hold the position of seat of arbitration and no objection was raised by the respondent against the award passed by the arbitrator it can be pointed that the shifting of venue/place of the arbitration is in accordance with the Section 20(1) (which deals with agreement of the parties on the place/ seat of arbitration) and not Section 20(3) (which deals with the discretion of arbitral tribunal to meet at any place for the convenience of the parties) of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.

So, once the seat of arbitration was shifted to Ahmedabad by mutual agreement the courts at Rajasthan ceased to have jurisdiction as the exclusive jurisdiction is now vested in the courts at Ahmedabad.

4. While referring to the case of BGS SGS Soma JV v. NHPC Ltd. in which it was observed that if a named place is identified in the arbitration agreement as the “venue of arbitration proceedings”, the use of the term “arbitration proceedings” means that the entire arbitration proceedings including the making of the award are to be conducted at such place of choice. In such a case, the venue of arbitration automatically assumes the position of the seat of arbitration⁸.
5. Relying on the judgment in BGS SGS Soma JV v. NHPC Ltd. the court held that the moment the parties agreed to shift the seat to Ahmedabad exclusive jurisdiction will vest with the courts at Ahmedabad unless anything contrary is mentioned.⁹

VI. CRITICAL APPRAISAL OF JUDGMENT

It can be said that this judgment makes it clear that where in an arbitration agreement there is no clause which mention that the change or shifting of seat can be done only by written agreement the parties can shift the seat by just by mutual consent and no written agreement is required.

In BGS Soma case it was observed that if any place is fixed as venue of arbitration agreement it signifies that the parties intend to hold the arbitration proceedings including

⁸ Utsav Garg, Seat vs Venue of Arbitration: The necessity, The absurdity and the road ahead (Nov. 17, 2023) <https://ijirl.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/SEAT-VS-VENUE-OF-ARBITRATION-THE-NECESSITY-THE-ABSURDITY-AND-THE-ROAD-AHEAD.pdf>

⁹ Supra 4

making of award at the agreed place and the same will be considered as the seat of arbitration. However, if any contrary intention is indicated that venue in the agreement will not be seat of arbitration then the above rule will not apply.

Speaking of the present case if we read the purchase order it provides that the venue of arbitration shall be Jaipur and if either of the party is not satisfied with the arbitrators' award, they can seek lawful remedies under the law of India. The jurisdiction for such actions will be the courts situated in the State of Rajasthan. Also, if we read the arbitral award it says, 'the parties have mutually agreed irrespective of a specific clause as to the (venue, that the place) of the arbitration would be at Ahmedabad and not at Jaipur'.

So, it can be said that as per the purchase order the exclusive jurisdiction was given to the courts of Rajasthan. And the arbitral award provides that the parties mutually agreed to shift the venue of arbitration and not the seat.

Later, in the case of BBR (India) (P) Ltd. v. S.P. Singla Constructions (P) Ltd. (2022) the Supreme Court relying on Inox Renewables Ltd. v. Jayesh Electricals Ltd. clarified that seat of the arbitration can be only changed when both the parties mutually agree to do so. The court also observed that once seat has been fixed by the arbitral tribunal under Section 20(2) it should remain fixed whereas venue of the arbitration can change in terms of Section 20(3).¹⁰

¹⁰ Prachi Bhardwaj, Change of venue does not result in change of the seat of arbitration; holding otherwise would create a recipe for litigation: Supreme Court (Nov. 19, 2023) [Change of venue does not result in change of the seat of arbitration; holding otherwise would create a recipe for litigation: Supreme Court | SCC Blog \(sconline.com\)](#)